

INCONSISTENCIES IN THE KATAKANA TRANSCRIPTION OF UZBEK PROPER NOUNS: A PHONOLOGICAL AND ORTHOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract: *This paper explores the inconsistencies found in the Katakana transcription of Uzbek proper nouns and place names. Despite the increasing interaction between Japanese and Uzbek languages, no unified system has been developed for representing Uzbek terms in Katakana. By analyzing transcriptions from historical and modern sources, the study reveals irregularities caused by a lack of phonetic alignment, diverse transcription practices, and the influence of Arabic and Cyrillic scripts. The paper highlights the phonological mismatches between Uzbek and Japanese and calls for a collaborative effort to establish a standard transcription system for improved accuracy and consistency in cross-linguistic communication.*

Keywords: *Uzbek proper nouns, Katakana transcription, phonological analysis, Arabic script, orthographic inconsistency, transliteration, Uzbek-Japanese linguistics, place names*

Introduction

Katakana, one of the Japanese writing systems, is primarily used to transcribe foreign words. Uzbek proper nouns and place names also fall into this category. However, representing Uzbek proper nouns in Katakana often leads to numerous issues, which can be observed in applications like Google Maps, textbooks, guidebooks, and translation processes.

This article analyzes the problems related to transcribing Uzbek proper nouns into the Katakana script. The research focuses on three main categories of issues:

1. Inconsistencies in the pronunciation of Uzbek proper nouns in Katakana transcription;
2. Lack of standardization in Katakana representations of Uzbek place names;
3. Absence of a clear transcription system for place names in Katakana.

Issues and Categories in Transcription

There is no specific standard system for transcribing Uzbek words into Japanese. Nonetheless, some general rules are followed:

- Stress in the original Uzbek word is usually not indicated;

- Consecutive vowels are separated using small u, i, or o signs;
- The glottal stop indicated by an apostrophe in Uzbek is generally omitted in transcription.

For instance, "O‘zbekiston" is rendered in Katakana as ウズベキスタン (U-zu-be-ki-su-ta-n).

Problems with Katakana Script and the Uzbek Language

Transcription methods often vary depending on the individual or organization, which results in inconsistent representations of names in different sources such as textbooks and maps.

Example:

- The Tashkent region is transcribed as タシケント (Tashikento) in some sources and タシュケント (Tashukento) in others.

Analysis of Transcription Standards

Using the guidebook "中央アジアサマルカンドとシルクロードの国々" (Countries of Central Asia: Samarkand and the Silk Road), several Uzbek proper nouns and place names were analyzed as follows:

Examples

- Amir Temur: アミール・ティムール (Amiiru Timuuru)
- Bibikhonim: ビビハニム (Bibi Hanimu)
- Shohizinda: シャーヒズインダ (Shaahi Zinda)
- Uzbekistan: ウズベキスタン (Uzubekisutan)
- Andijan: アンディジャン (Andijan)

Phonetic Analysis

The Japanese sound system does not include many Uzbek-specific phonemes. Therefore, certain substitutions are used:

- The "v" sound is represented using the character ヴ;
- The "q" sound is replaced with カ;
- The voiced uvular fricative "g" is replaced with ガ;
- The voiceless uvular fricative "x" is replaced with ハ.

Differences from Old Uzbek Script

In some cases, transcription is based on Arabic script rather than modern Uzbek orthography. For example:

- Amir Temur is written in Arabic as تيمور امير. Its Katakana version includes a length mark, likely derived from Arabic script conventions.
- In Bibikhonim, the segment "خا" is rendered as ハ (ha) in Katakana.

- The length marker in Shohizinda may be due to the presence of "alif" in the Arabic spelling.

In other instances, transcription is clearly based on contemporary pronunciation rather than historical orthographies.

Conclusion

This article investigated the inconsistencies in pronouncing Uzbek proper nouns in Katakana transcription. The study revealed the following findings:

1. Some transcriptions are based on Arabic script, while others rely on phonetic pronunciation;
2. The same word may appear in multiple transcription forms, indicating a lack of standardization;
3. The absence of unified rules has led to confusion and inconsistency in Katakana representations.

To resolve this issue, it is necessary to develop a standardized transcription system for Uzbek proper nouns into Katakana through collaboration between Uzbek and Japanese linguists. This would allow for more coherent and understandable representations of Uzbekistan-related content in Japanese.

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